

AUTHOR'S PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *Pedagogical technologies play an important role in the education of medical specialists. One of the main tasks of the author's pedagogical technologies in medicine is the formation of students' deep understanding of medical knowledge and skills, as well as the development of critical thinking and the ability to work independently. To achieve these goals, various teaching methods are used, such as problem-based learning, project activities, case method, interactive lectures, simulation training, and others.*

Keywords: *author's pedagogical technology, medical education, simulation training, problem-based learning, case method, project activity, online learning.*

Introduction

In modern medical education, special attention is paid to the development and implementation of author's pedagogical technologies. Medical universities are actively looking for new approaches to teaching students to provide them with the comprehensive knowledge and skills necessary for successful professional activities.

One of the key goals of the use of author's pedagogical technologies in medical universities is to increase the efficiency of the educational process. This is achieved through the creation of innovative educational programs that take into account the specifics of the medical industry and modern requirements for the quality of medical care.

Modern medicine requires specialists not only deep theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills, the ability to quickly adapt to new conditions and technologies. In this regard, the author's pedagogical technologies are of particular importance, which make the learning process more effective, interesting and corresponding to the individual needs of each student.

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What is the author's pedagogical technology?

Author's pedagogical technology is a unique teaching system developed by a specific teacher or a group of authors. It includes a set of methods, techniques, teaching tools, organizational forms and conditions aimed at achieving certain educational goals.

Advantages of author's pedagogical technologies in medicine:

- Individualization of learning: The ability to adapt the learning process to the needs of each student, taking into account their level of knowledge, interests and learning style.
- Increased motivation: Through the use of interesting and non-standard teaching methods, students become more active and interested in learning the material.

- Development of practical skills: Emphasis is placed on the development of practical skills, which is especially important for future medical workers.
- Formation of professional competencies: Students acquire not only the knowledge, but also the skills necessary for successful work in the medical field.
- Creating a creative atmosphere: Author's technologies contribute to the development of creative thinking and innovative approaches to solving professional problems.

Examples of author's pedagogical technologies in medicine:

Simulation training: Use of simulators to practice practical skills (e.g., surgery, first aid). Simulation training is one of the most effective methods of training future medical specialists. It involves the use of medical simulators, virtual patients and other training technologies to simulate real clinical situations. This allows students to acquire practical skills without risk to patients and increases the level of professional competence.

One of the examples of author's pedagogical technologies used in medical universities is the method of problem-based learning. This approach allows students to actively participate in the educational process, solving real-world clinical problems and developing decision-making skills in the face of uncertainty. This method of training contributes to the formation of professional competence of future doctors and improves the quality of medical care.

Case method: Study of real clinical cases, which allows students to apply theoretical knowledge in practice.

Project activities: Students carry out individual or group projects aimed at solving urgent medical problems.

Online learning: Using digital technologies to create interactive learning materials and organize distance learning.

Particular attention in the author's pedagogical technologies is paid to the development of communication skills in future medical specialists. Doctors and nurses must be able to communicate effectively with patients, colleagues, and other healthcare actors. For this purpose, various methods of communication training, role-playing, empathy training and interprofessional interaction are used.

An important aspect of the author's pedagogical technologies in medicine is the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the educational process. This includes the use of e-learning materials, online courses, webinars, multimedia presentations, and other modern educational resources. The use of ICT makes the educational process more accessible, interactive and effective.

In addition, the author's pedagogical technologies include the use of modern information technologies in the educational process. This allows students to access up-to-date medical information, use simulators to practice skills, and conduct distance learning. Such innovative approaches help to increase students' motivation and improve the quality of learning material.

An important aspect of the author's pedagogical technologies is the individualization of the educational process. Medical universities strive to create conditions for the development of individual abilities of each student, taking into account his needs and characteristics. This can be achieved through the organization of mentoring support, individual consultations and the development of personalized training plans.

Development of the author's pedagogical technology

The development of the author's pedagogical technology is a complex and creative process, which includes the following stages:

1. Needs analysis: Definition of learning objectives, study of the characteristics of the classroom and existing educational resources.
2. Selection of methods and techniques: Selection of teaching methods and techniques that will be the most effective for achieving the set goals.
3. Curriculum Development: Creating instructional materials that are appropriate to the chosen methods and techniques.
4. Organization of the educational process: Planning of training sessions, determining the roles of the teacher and students.
5. Evaluation of efficiency: Evaluation of the effectiveness of the developed technology using various methods (questionnaires, testing).

Conclusion

Author's pedagogical technologies play an important role in the modernization of medical education. They make the learning process more effective, interesting and in line with modern requirements. However, for the successful implementation of author's technologies, it is necessary to constantly improve and adapt to changing conditions.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of author's pedagogical technologies in medical universities plays an important role in the training of highly qualified specialists. These innovative approaches contribute to increasing the efficiency of the educational process, the formation of students' professional competencies and improving the quality of medical care.

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